

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B271
Date: 25 February 2007
Take Off: 10:28:21Z
Landing: 16:18:46Z
Flight Time: 5h50m25

Campaign: GFDEX – Mesoscale Cyclone (Plan 41)

Operating Area: North of Iceland (Targ Obs)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Kent Moore	University of Toronto
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	AVAPS	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / AVAPS Training / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
9	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Egill Kristjansson	University of Oslo
10	Mission Scientist 3	Ivan Fore	University of Oslo
11	Mission Scientist 4	Idaar Barstad	University of Bergen
12	Mission Scientist 5	Carling Hay	University of Toronto
13	Observer	Margaret Munro	Canadian Press Agency
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Flight Track:

B271 Track 25-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b271
 Date: 25 Feb 2007
 Project: GFDEX - Mesoscale cyclone
 Location: N of Iceland to E of Greenland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
094146		Start-Up	0.08 kft	236	63'59.66N, 22'37.65W
100707		INU	0.08 kft	236	To Navigate
102821		T/O	1.4 kft	011	Keflavik
103826		Videos	18.6 kft	058	Start DFC & FFC
115024	121156	Run 1.1	25.0 kft	078	
115053		Sonde	25.0 kft	078	Launch #01
120147		Sonde	25.0 kft	349	Launch #02
121047		Videos	25.0 kft	353	Change Tapes
121156		Sonde	25.0 kft	352	Launch #03
121643	123318	Run 1.2	25.0 kft	162	Launch #05
122547		Sonde	25.0 kft	150	Launch #04
123318	124551	Sonde	25.0 - 26.1 kft	148	Launch #05
124318	124953	Profile 1	25.0 kft	270	
124544		Sonde	26.1 kft	271	Launch #06
124953	140236	Run 2.1	28.0 kft	271	
125343		Sonde	28.0 kft	269	Launch #07
125400		Event	28.0 kft	269	Contrailing
130208		Sonde	28.0 kft	271	Launch #08
130936		Sonde	28.0 kft	270	Launch #09
131730		Sonde	28.0 kft	271	Launch #10
132512		Sonde	28.0 kft	272	Launch #11
133241		Sonde	28.0 kft	272	Launch #12
134016		Sonde	28.0 kft	270	Launch #13
134743		Sonde	28.0 kft	269	Launch #14
135444		Sonde	28.0 kft	268	Launch #15
140143		Sonde	28.0 kft	268	Launch #16
140237	142924	Profile 2	28.0 - -.04 kft	280	To 100',QNH1016
141234		Videos	14.5 kft	126	Change Tapes
142924	151447	Run 3.1	-.04 - 0.28 kft	086	At 100'
143106		Heimann	-.02 kft	090	Cal
150223		Videos	0.18 kft	083	UFC & DFC
150238		Heimann	0.19 kft	082	Cal
152425		Event	23.9 kft	230	Contrailing
153158		Transit	26.0 kft	221	Return to base
161846		Land	0.12 kft	020	Keflavik
162255		Shutdown	0.13 kft	178	63'58.43N, 22'35.80W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B271 Track 25-FEB-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – B271 – 25 February 2007
Mesoscale Cyclone (Plan 41)

Mission Scientists: Kent Moore, Mel Shapiro, Jon Egill Kristjansson, Ivan Fore, Margaret Munro, Carling Hay, Idar Barstad

Aims

- Investigate the structure of the mesoscale cyclone situated to the north and east of Iceland
- Map out the low-level structure of the northerly flow associated with the low including the heat fluxes across the ice edge
- Total dropsondes 16

GFD41	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1030	Take off Keflavík , transit to 67N 5W	470	~90	~90
2		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due north to 69N, 6W. Dropsonde release at start, middle (68N, 6W) and end of leg (69N,6W). 3 in total	120	~25	~115
3		Straight level run at 25-30kft to 68N, 3W with dropsonde at middle (68.5N, 4.5W) and end of leg (68N, 3W). 2 in total	130	~25	~130
4		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due west to 68N, 23W with dropsondes every 40 nm. 11 in total	440	~90	~220
5		Stacked descent to 100 ft at (68N, 23W).		~	~
6		Straight level run at 100 ft due east to 68N, 16W	160	~40	~260
7		Transit to Keflavík.	300	~60	~320

Mesoscale cyclone - GFDex Plan 41

68,94
5W

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B271** Date **Res 28** Name **Moore** Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:30					Take off.
11:30					60N 11W clear sky to the NW
					higher cloud to the E
11:36:00				66°30' } 9W }	comma feature to the W
11:40					stratus deck to E more variable to the W
11:45					Wind speed map 28 m/s
11:51					1st drop sonde
					Clear sky to the E
					Q/R 67N 11'
					EW leg at this latitude low latitude
12:00					clear sky to E.
12:01					Dropsonde #2.
12:04					higher cloud to W windy E
12:11					Dropsonde #3

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.271** Date Name Moore Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:15				6915W	clear sky to the R
12:20					small clouds to the R
12:21					ditto
12:26					Dropsonde #4
12:29					small cloud to R
12:31					appear to have cut through vortex max on both V bound (E) SE bound legs //
12:33					Dropsonde #5 (bad?)
12:34					turning W interesting cloud to the R
12:39					Some light turbulence
12:43					climb to 2910 feet
12:45					Dropsonde #6 (bad data)
12:53					Dropsonde #7

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.271**... Date Name **M. O. I. R. O.**... Page **3** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:00					ozone peak @ 120 ppb
13:02					Dropsonde # 8
13:09					Dropsonde # 9
13:10					Ozone spike 7150 ppb
13:15					evidence of higher cloud
13:17					Dropsonde # 10
13:19					Cloud streets to the E(N)
13:21					clear sky to the W(S) evidence of higher cloud
13:15					broad ozone max 7180 ppb
13:25					Dropsonde # 11
13:29					cloud streets NS to the N
13:32					Dropsonde # 12
13:32					ozone dropping ultra broad max
13:34					clear skies ahead
13:38					Clear sky @ start of sea ice
13:40					Dropsonde # 13 ~ 20W isolated streamers to the S
13:45					sea ice to the N

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.271**... Date **Feb 25** Name Page **4** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:47					Dropsonde # 13 14
13:49					Greenland to the N 120 nm
13:54					curtain in sea ice Dropsonde # 15
13:58					close to ice edge
14:00					ice edge Greenland closest approach
					surface temp dropping
14:01					Dropsonde # 14 16
14:05					began descent
14:21					curtain in sea ice to the north
14:26					complex surface evidence of small \oplus waves
14:28					500 feet beam to fall turbulence
14:29					100 feet
14:38					12 m/s moderate chop

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.271** Date Name Page **5** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:40					14 m/s
14:42					13 m/s appeared to have levelled off now decaying
14:43					1. The jet is
14:48					another jet WS picking up 15 m/s
14:52					evidence of clouds ahead.
14:53					large WS lots of white caps
14:56					another peak
14:57					winds peak at ~20
14:00					start of "high clouds"
15:02					clouds ahead evidence of F20 clouds

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B271

Date: 25/02/07

Operator: KFT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
					NOISY			NOISY			During Taxi, T/O
10:28											Heaters on
10:31											FFSSP Base values increased
10:41											FL220 2DP data rate reduced
10:58			Restarted								Base values increased
											During transit, no real images.
11:50:55	156	0.06	1	-	0	0		0	0		FL250 Sonde 1; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:01:50	167	0.06	2	-	0	0		0	0		FL250 Sonde 2; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:11:58	165	0.06	2	-	0	0		0	0		FL250 Sonde 3; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:16:43	176	0.06	2	-	0	0		0	0		Start Run 1
12:25:48	170	0.06	3	-	0	0		0	0		FL250 Sonde 4; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:33:19	135	0.06	4	-	0	0		0	0		FL250 Sonde 5; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:43:18	134	0.06	5	-	0	0		0	0		FL250 Start Profile 1
12:45:44	130	0.06	5	-	0	0		0	0		FL260 Sonde 6
12:48:00	115	0.06	6	-	0	0		0	0		FL270 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:49:54	98	0.06	6	-	0	0		0	0		FL280 Run2; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
12:53:45	133	0.06	6	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 7; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
13:01											FFSSP annulus base value incr
13:02:01	134	0.06	6	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 8; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
13:09:38	138	0.06	6	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 9; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
13:17:32	81	0.07	7	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 10; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
13:25:14	146	0.06	7	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 11 – PCASP Vref dropouts
13:32:43	125	0.06	7	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 12; PCASP restarted
13:40:18	105	0.07	7	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 13; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
13:47:42	109	0.06	8	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 14; 2DP, 2DC NOISY
13:54:46	103	0.07	8	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 15; 2DP NOISY
14:01:44	98	0.07	8	-	0	0		0	0		Sonde 16; 2DP NOISY
											Nothing during descent
14:14:04	125	0.06	9	-	0	0		0	0		FL130
14:15:05	107	0.06	2806	-	0	0		0	0		FL120
14:16:20	92	0.08	3797	-	0	0		0	0		FL110
14:21:58	193	0.07	0	-	0	0		0	0		FL060 FFSSP RESTARTED!!
14:23:00	348	0.06	0	-	0	0		0	0		FL050
14:24:00	416	0.06	0	-	0	0		0	0		FL040

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B271

Date: 25/02/07

Operator: KFT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:25:30	332	0.06	0	-	0	0		0	0		FL030
14:26:28	231	0.6	1	-	0	0		0	0		FL020; PCASP Vref dropouts
14:27:50	333	0.06	12	-	0	0		0	0		FL010
14:29:24	400	0.06	88	-	0	0		0	0		100FT ASL END PROFILE 2
14:33			RESTARTED								2dc, 2dp STILL NOISY
15:08:00	150	0.11	8	-	2.5	400	8,3	266	400	8	
15:10:00	124	0.17	9	-	13	800	8,3,	2016	1600	8	
15:12:00	106	0.09	12	-	22	750	8,3	3291	1600	8,3	
15:14:00	95	0.09	15	-	7	750	8,3	2008	1600	8,3	
15:14:49	1-7	0.09	16	-	19	775	3,8	3741	1600	3,8	End Run at 500FT
15:15:45	203	0.06	37	-	7	550	3,8	5808	1200	3,8	FL020
15:16:30	57	0.08	39	-	8	800	3,8	1525	1200	3,8	FL040
15:17:17	50	0.08	40	-		800	3,9	66	800	3,8	FL060
15:18:00	62	0.08	41	-	2	800	8	266	800	8	FL080
15:18:34	51	0.08	42	-	0.5	600	8	166	600	8	FL100
15:19:15	24	0.07	45	-	16	400	8		400	8	FL120
15:20:02	73	0.06	48	-		400	8		400	8	FL140
15:20:43	71	0.06	48	-	0	0		0	0		FL160 NOISE ON 2DP
15:22:20	71	0.06	48	-	-	-		-	-		FL200 Noise ON 2dp and 2dc
15:23:12	59	0.06	48	-							FL220 Noise on 2dp, 2dc
			Signal base incr								
15:24:38	129	0.05	48	-	-	-		-	-		FL240
			Base values inc		NOISY			NOISY			FFSSP increased base values.
16:09:00			Resarted								FFSSP increased base values
16:13:											

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B271 **T/O:** 10:28:21
Date of flight: 25/02/07 **Land:** 16:18:46

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B271
Date of Flight: 25/02/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	18197 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 322325
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 64771 Blocks written = 64771 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 102500 End = 162500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Noise on 2DC other than 150915 – 152200 No 2DP images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 092500 End = 162500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 150000 End = 153000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 153000 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 928, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	Y	<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B271
Date of Flight: 25/02/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 093000 162000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK? Y

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B271	Date	25/02/2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	SWH/BW

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. windata? PTH data? Lat/Long</i>
115054	1	Launch	375.70 -46.00 51.73 215.10 25.90 -14.40 -6.034600 67.003900 7625.60 0
120005	1	Land	1000.65 0.52 70.70 283.98 9.26 - 10.78 -5.898225 67.040017 444.37 8
120150	2	Launch	373.94 -9.76 1.10 183.69 81.29 -0.01 -5.698111 68.004715 8065.73
121026	2	Land	997.67 0.51 999.00 263.33 10.54 -10.56 -5.587529 68.047747 99999.00
121157	3	Launch	375.90 -45.50 32.25 197.00 19.50 -14.70 -5.964000 68.989400 7621.20 0
122059	3	Land	993.92 0.71 95.38 178.86 10.95 -11.28 -5.909323 69.056391 484.95
122549	4	Launch	122549.20 373.04 -5.12 1.41 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000
123245	4	Land	997.16 1.38 999.00 217.03 10.55 -11.59 -3.956376 68.549743 99999.00
123319	5	Launch	372.38 2.69 1.55 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 8247.03
124009	5	Land	999.38 1.65 66.67 231.73 8.79 -11.15 -2.932044 68.053225 99999.00
124545	6	Launch	358.60 -47.30 28.94 214.20 28.00 -14.60 -5.246100 67.951400 7949.00
125519	6	Land	996.85 1.20 81.88 252.19 9.17 -10.16 -5.127680 68.007840 486.23
125345	7	Launch	328.70 -51.40 33.69 219.10 23.90 -15.80 -7.002400 68.042100 8546.50
130341	7	Land	997.05 0.23 96.83 268.75 11.23 -10.96 -6.847822 68.083009 526.55
130201	8	Launch	326.67 2.72 2.14 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 9298.21
130757	8	Land	996.40 0.05 88.20 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 99999.00
130942	9	Launch	328.90 -50.80 16.25 242.40 12.10 -15.30 -10.555700 68.167000 8541.80
131911	9	Land	1000.85 -0.28 90.07 320.25 15.71 - 11.61 -10.437299 68.126796 99999.00
131733	10	Launch	328.90 -51.00 15.12 280.20 7.90 -14.90 -12.332100 68.200300 8541.80 0
132739	10	Land	1002.56 -1.40 95.18 323.64 17.23 - 11.31 -12.222444 68.129158 582.37 6
132515	11	Launch	328.90 -52.40 16.41 348.20 7.90 -15.00 -14.120600 68.215000 8542.20 0
133526	11	Land	1006.76 -1.78 91.66 334.33 16.67 - 10.21 -14.054026 68.142528 575.37 8
133242	12	Launch	328.80 -53.30 18.51 3.60 9.60 -14.40 -15.896400 68.210000 8544.80 0
134244	12	Land	1010.58 -3.11 90.60 332.95 15.99 -10.46 -15.888005 68.151961 567.48 6
134018	13	Launch	328.80 -53.30 15.46 14.90 8.80 -14.80 -17.691600 68.185600 8544.20 0
135002	13	Land	1012.89 -3.68 71.66 335.30 19.22 - 10.74 -17.697696 68.125000 564.19 7

Flight:

B271

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 15/03/2007
12:11:57**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

14/03/2007 15:55:09

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B271

Date: 25 Feb 2007

Instruments

1. CO – Signal noisy. Great fluctuations pre-flight including negative.
2. TWC – Dew point on HORACE reading zero all the time. Think it's because offset (Para 70) in hor_calib.dat is higher (1380), than Para 70 actual DRS value (920), resulting in negative TWC values being calculated. Changed offset in hor_calib.dat to 900.
3. FFC Camera Window – appears to be smudges on window, may be on the inside.
4. Camera Demist – Causes interference i.e. flickering on FFC when selected ON.
5. RVSM – TAS dropped out to zero in flight. Reset PAFT DLU CB then okay.
6. Sonde No. 08 – failed, no data received.
7. Sonde No. 15 – no data until ~ 900mb.
8. TWC – Status light flashing on descent into Keflavik. Suspect Sample Temperature (Para 72) on lower limit. Had been okay in flight with temperature down to -50°C .

Aircraft

1. Burst pipe in galley pre-flight. Repaired before flight but no piped water available in flight.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Flight Manager's Data Processing Status

Flight No: B271
Flight Manager: MS

Date of flight: 25/02/07

Mfd data must be backed up within a week.

If it can't be done by the Cloud Physics Operator in that time the **FM must back it up**

<u>On day of flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Update Database & Note BBR Fit	Database	25/2/07
Create Fltcons & check BBR fit	Option 9	25/2/07
Transfer & process Data	Option 2	25/2/07
Ftp qldata to BADC	project_spaces/faam/quicklook	n/a
Check Rawdata	flight_plot	25/2/07
Raw data to BADC	Option 7 this failed, sent it manually	26/2/07
Copy & Convert Fltsumm file	Copy from optical to fltsumm directory Set def fltsumm run tarexec:convert_summ	26/2/07
Edit Fltsumm/ send to BADC	Option 10	27/2/07
Copy Flight logs to Seagate	Flight Logs	28/2/07
Download photos, clear camera & email Doug	To Flight Logs and Turb Probe Photos	26/2/07
Ftp CGPS.bin file to BADC	project_spaces/faam/javad_gps	2/3/07
Check MFDdata	flight_plot	26/2/07

<u>On day after flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Ftp PSAP to FLOODS	Bnnn_psap_data	n/a
Merge PSAP into mfddata	wave .run mergepsap bnnn_mfda (b,c)	n/a
Record any MFD changes	edit mfddata:mfddata.txt	n/a
NETCDF to BADC	Option 4	27/2/07
Upload .nc from BADC	To USB stick (WS_FTP Pro)	27/2/07
Data quality check	Run Checkg on Linux pc	27/2/07
Ftp quality file to BADC	/incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core	27/2/07
Print out quality file	put in Faults Book	28/2/07
Backup raw data to optical then to firesafe	Option 6	27/2/07
Backup mfd if Cloud Physics Operator can't	MFD Backup Instructions.doc	
Ftp mfd to BADC	Not yet set up	
Video tapes to PI or cupboard	Video Tape Log	To PI 27/2/07
Complete & save this form	Data Processing Logs	02/03/07

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B271:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Kent Moore
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	10 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x For/Rearward Facing Cameras

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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Daily weather summary 25 February 2007

<p>Large scale situation today:</p>	<p>A high pressure system is over Greenland, with northerly flow over east Greenland, and southerly over western Greenland. The North Atlantic is dominated by low pressure systems. A cyclone situated to the northeast of Newfoundland deepened to a 966 hPa central pressure. The cyclone to the west of Ireland has slowly faded and moved eastward toward the UK. The cyclone to the East of Greenland (5W;71N) deepened to 993 hPa.</p>
<p>Features of interest:</p>	<p>The mesoscale cyclone (polar low) to the east of Greenland deepened with well defined clouds to the west and south. A mesoscale cyclone is forming over southeast Iceland.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Analysis chart valid 00 UTC Sun 25 FEB 2007</p> </div>
<p>Action:</p>	<p>A mesoscale cyclone and targeted observation flight to the south of Iceland is planned.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 24-48 hours:</p>	<p>UK global model predicts: the North Atlantic is still characterized by the low pressure systems. The polar low moves southwest as it fills. The cyclone over UK moves eastward and dissipates in 48 hours. The cyclone to the northwest of Newfoundland maintains and splits a mesoscale cyclone moving eastward. The centre of mesoscale cyclone situates south of 55N, so there is no significant jets in next few days.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 48-96 hours:</p>	<p>On UK global weather maps, the mesoscale cyclone northwest of Newfoundland moves eastward, with centre located 52N. What needs more attention is the trough at western Greenland on 1 March and that moves eastward. It develops into mesoscale cyclone on 2 March and produces barrier jets. However this system is pretty weak on ECMWF weather maps.</p>

Drop Points 25 February 2007

E-W Cross Section, 25 February 2007

N-S Cross Section, 25 February 2007

